

Complexes of Copper(II)Carboxylates with Dimethylsulphoxide

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Complexes of some copper(II)carboxylates with dimethylsulphoxide of the general formula, $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$ ($\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, *o*-, *m*- or *p*- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, *o*-, *m*- or *p*- ClC_6H_4 , *p*- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, CH_2Cl or CHCl_2) have been prepared and characterized by analytical, electrical conductance, visible and ir spectral and magnetic susceptibility data.

DIMETHYLSULPHOXIDE (DMSO) is both a sulphur and an oxygen donor ligand and its behaviour as a ligand towards metals and non-metals has been investigated¹. One point of importance in considering the structures of its complexes is the identification of the donor atom. Copper and most other metal ions have been found to coordinate through oxygen with DMSO. However, in some cases infrared evidence suggests $\text{M} \leftarrow \text{S}$ bonding². Some work has been done on the complexes of this ligand with copper(II) carboxylates³⁻⁵. In the present investigation a number of complexes of various copper(II)arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates with DMSO have been prepared and characterized with the view to investigate the effect, if any, of the strength of the carboxylic acid on the nature and stereochemistry of the complexes isolated.

Experimental

Copper(II)carboxylates were prepared by standard methods^{6,7}. Dimethylsulphoxide used was 'Chemapol' extra-pure grade.

Preparation of the complexes: The complexes were prepared by direct addition of the ligand to an acetone or methanol solution of the respective copper(II)carboxylate in 1 : 1 molar ratio and subjecting the reaction mixture to usual techniques of concentration, crystallization and further purification by recrystallization. Any change in molar ratio of the reactants did not affect the stoichiometry of the complex. However, maximum yield was obtained when the reactants were taken in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

Analysis: Copper was analysed gravimetrically as CuSCN . Carbon and hydrogen contents of the complexes were determined in the microanalytical laboratory of this department.

Physical measurements: Molar conductance of the complexes was determined on their millimolar solutions in 1,4-dioxane and methanol by using Elico type CM 82T conductivity bridge and a conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.5011. Magnetic

measurements of the complexes were carried out at room temperature by 'Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the standard. Absorption spectra of the complexes were scanned in chloroform in 1 cm matched quartz cells in the range 320-800 nm on Beckman D. B. spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra of some complexes were got scanned in the range 320-1000 nm on Carl Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra of the complexes in the region 400-4000 cm^{-1} in KBr were recorded on Pye Unicam SP 2000 infrared spectrophotometer.

The analytical data of the complexes prepared are presented in Table 1. Conductance, magnetic moments and electronic spectra are cited in Table 2. Important infrared bands and their probable assignments are given in Table 3.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES WITH DMSO

Compound	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	Cu	C	H
$\text{Cu}(\text{benzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	16.23 (16.56)	49.89 (50.06)	3.99 (4.17)
$\text{Cu}(\text{o-methylbenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	14.92 (15.44)	52.16 (52.49)	4.78 (4.86)
$\text{Cu}(\text{m-methylbenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	15.04 (15.44)	52.40 (52.49)	4.81 (4.86)
$\text{Cu}(\text{p-methylbenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	15.41 (15.44)	52.29 (52.49)	4.69 (4.86)
$\text{Cu}(\text{o-chlorobenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	14.23 (14.04)	42.34 (42.43)	2.88 (3.09)
$\text{Cu}(\text{m-chlorobenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	13.82 (14.04)	42.29 (42.43)	2.94 (3.09)
$\text{Cu}(\text{p-chlorobenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	13.91 (14.04)	42.40 (42.43)	3.01 (3.09)
$\text{Cu}(\text{p-methoxybenzoate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	14.22 (14.32)	48.53 (48.70)	4.21 (4.50)
$\text{Cu}(\text{monochloroacetate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	19.43 (19.34)	21.77 (21.91)	3.19 (3.28)
$\text{Cu}(\text{dichloroacetate})_2 \cdot \text{DMSO}$	15.79 (15.98)	18.01 (18.11)	1.96 (2.01)

Results and Discussion

The complexes are green crystalline solids which are quite stable in air and soluble in common

TABLE 2—MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES WITH DMSO

Compound	Molar conductance (mole ⁻¹ ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)		Magnetic data		Electronic spectral data (nm)
	In 1,4-dioxane	In methanol	μ_{eff} B.M.	Temp. K	
Cu(benzoate) ₂ .DMSO	0.093	26.04	1.59	297	685 ^a
Cu(<i>o</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	—	—	1.52	297	690 ^a
Cu(<i>m</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	—	—	1.45	297	675 ^b
Cu(<i>p</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	0.029	—	1.58	298	680 ^a
Cu(<i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	0.18	44.13	1.43	298	692 ^a 710 ^b
Cu(<i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	0.029	26.47	1.49	298	—
Cu(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	0.042	—	1.41	298	—
Cu(monochloroacetate) ₂ .DMSO	0.061	54.54	1.43	297	704 ^a
Cu(dichloroacetate) ₂ .DMSO	0.029	61.93	1.60	298	728 ^a

a : In chloroform ; b : Diffuse reflectance spectra.

TABLE 3—IMPORTANT INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES WITH DMSO

Compound	Ligand vibrations		Carboxylate group vibrations		
	ν (SO)	$\Delta\nu$ (SO)	ν_{asy} (COO)	ν_{sy} (COO)	$\Delta\nu$ (COO)
DMSO	1055	—	—	—	—
Cu(benzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1025	30	1620	1400	220
Cu(<i>o</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1020	35	1620	1395	225
Cu(<i>m</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1020	35	1615	1400	215
Cu(<i>p</i> -methylbenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1020	35	1605	1405	200
Cu(<i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1015	40	1615	1410	205
Cu(<i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1018	37	1630	1390	240
Cu(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate) ₂ .DMSO	1015	40	1610	1400	210
Cu(monochloroacetate) ₂ .DMSO	1035	20	1645	1415	230
Cu(dichloroacetate) ₂ .DMSO	1035	20	1670	1405	265

organic solvents. On the basis of their elemental analyses (Table 1), they have been assigned the general formula, Cu(O₂CR)₂.DMSO (R = C₆H₅, *o*-, *m*- or *p*-CH₃C₆H₄, *o*-, *m*- or *p*-ClC₆H₄, *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄, CH₂Cl or CHCl₂). Conductance values of these complexes in 1,4-dioxane and methanol (Table 2) are far less than the values reported for uni-univalent electrolytes in these solvents^{8,9} and indicate that these complexes are nonelectrolytic in nature.

The magnetic moment values of these complexes at room temperature fall in the range 1.41-1.60 B.M. (Table 2), which are less than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. and close to the value of 1.40 B.M. found in so many other copper(II)carboxylates and their 1 : 1 adducts¹⁰. This suggests that these complexes have a dimeric carboxylate bridged structure similar to that of copper(II)acetate monohydrate.

A comparison of the magnetic moments of DMSO complexes of copper(II)methylbenzoates and chloroacetates with those of parent non-adduct copper(II)carboxylates indicates that the presence of DMSO molecules in the two terminal positions in the complexes does not affect the spin-spin interaction between the two paramagnetic centres of the non-adduct copper(II)carboxylate. This is in agreement with the observation¹¹ that strongly antiferromagnetic uncomplexed copper(II)carboxylates on forming 1 : 1 adducts with donor ligands do not

undergo appreciable change in their magnetic properties. However, in the DMSO complexes of copper(II)chlorobenzoates magnetic studies show that the original uncomplexed polymeric copper(II)carboxylates undergo a substantial change in their magnetic properties as the ligand forces them to adopt a dimeric carboxylate configuration in these complexes. This is in agreement with the observations on the mono-pyridine adducts of polymeric copper(II)*m*- and *p*-chlorobenzoates^{12,13}. All this discussion shows that at the present moment it is difficult to pinpoint the circumstances in which the ligand can change appreciably the magnetic properties of the uncomplexed parent copper(II)carboxylate in their mono-adducts of the type Cu(O₂CR)₂L. It is also not possible to establish any correlation between the properties of the ligand such as basicity, steric characteristics and the structural and magnetic peculiarities of Cu(O₂CR)₂L adducts unless detailed magnetic and structural studies of these systems are available. It is difficult to say whether basicity or any other property of the ligand can alter the magnetic properties of the parent copper(I)carboxylates in their 1 : 1 adducts or not.

The complexes exhibit only one broad band in the region 675-728 nm (Table 2), analogous to band I of the copper(II)carboxylate systems characteristic of a distorted octahedral geometry. This band may be assigned to a dxz, dyz → d_{x²-y²} transition. Band

II, which is usually observed as a shoulder in most of the dimeric complexes could not be traced in the present complexes although these complexes have been shown by their 1 : 1 stoichiometry and magnetic studies to be of dimeric character. These results coupled with the observations that this band is also found in many non-dimeric complexes^{1,4} lead to the conclusion that the presence of band II is not a diagnostic test for dimeric structure and its absence in the present complexes does not rule out their possibility of having a carboxylate bridged structure.

The important infrared spectral bands observed in the complexes are given in Table 3. S-O stretching vibrations in these complexes fall around 1015-1035 cm^{-1} as compared to the corresponding frequency in the free ligand occurring at 1055 cm^{-1} and thus exhibit a decrease of 20-40 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{SO})$, pointing that DMSO in these complexes coordinates to the metal ion through its oxygen atom as observed in its complexes with other copper(II) salts. The magnitude of decrease, though considerably low as compared to that usually observed in DMSO complexes of other copper(II) salts, is quite similar to the values reported earlier in mono-adducts of DMSO with copper(II)carboxylates indicating that the DMSO ligand in the present complexes is weakly coordinated⁵.

The COO symmetric and asymmetric frequencies in these complexes fall in the regions 1390-1415 and 1605-1670 cm^{-1} , respectively. Their separation values (Δ) fall in the range 200-265 cm^{-1} which is greater than that reported for the corresponding non-adduct copper(II)carboxylates but is in agreement with the Δ values reported for dimeric com-

plexes of copper(II)carboxylates with DMSO and other oxygen donors^{1,5}.

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